

THE ROLE OF THE INVESTMENT CLIMATE IN INCREASING FOREIGN TRADE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: THEORY AND ANALYSIS

O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TASHQI SAVDOSINI OSHIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITINING ROLI: NAZARIYA VA TAHLIL

¹Khazratkulova
Markhabo Azizbek kizi

¹Master’s student of Tashkent State University of Economics.
E-mail: khazratkulova@gmail.com

Annotatsiya Annotation

Eng - This article studies the essence of investment attractiveness, the opinions of foreign and domestic economists on increasing investment attractiveness in attracting foreign direct investment. International practice is analyzed in terms of increasing the country’s foreign trade figures by attracting foreign direct investment. The article also studies the foreign trade practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and formulates practical recommendations and theoretical proposals for increasing foreign trade indicators by improving the investment climate.

Uzb - Ushbu maqolada investitsion jozibadorlikning mazmun-mohiyati, to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish haqida iqtisodchi xorijiy va mahalliy olimlarning fikr-mulohazalari o‘rganilgan. To‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish orqali mamlakat tashqi savdo suratlarining oshishi yuzasidan xalqaro amaliyot tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, maqolada O‘zbekiston Respublikasi tashqi savdo amaliyoti o‘rganilgan bo‘lib, investitsion muhitni yaxshilash orqali tashqi savdo ko‘rsatkichlarini oshirish borasida amaliy tavsiyalar hamda nazariy takliflar shakllantirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Keywords:

❖ *investment attractiveness, investment environment, foreign trade, foreign investment, investment potential, investment project, export-import, balance of payments, trade balance, surplus, deficit, investment policy, investment flow.*

❖ *investitsion jozibadorlik, investitsion muhit, tashqi savdo, xorijiy sarmoya, investitsiya potentsiali, investitsion loyiha, eksport-import, to‘lov balansi, savdo balansi, profitsit, defitsit, investitsiya siyosati, investitsiya oqimi.*

Introduction.

No matter which developed and developed country economy we consider, we can see that improving investment attractiveness has influenced the growth of the country’s recipient position. Therefore, our country has determined its own direction of development of the national economy. And the role of investments in the effective organization

and development of socio-economic processes in the country is incomparable. Because if the investment policy in a particular country is correctly established, and the investment climate is well created, then it will be possible to achieve growth in the gross domestic product (GDP), development of foreign trade and social stability in this country.

At the same time, a deep analysis of the path of development that our country has taken, the fact that today the world market situation is changing dramatically and competition is intensifying in the context of globalization, requires the development and implementation of a completely new approach and principles for the more stable and rapid development of our country. Therefore, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. DP-6o “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 [1]”, a number of final tasks were set in terms of reforming the national economy, including liberalizing foreign trade, tax and financial policies, supporting entrepreneurship and guaranteeing the inviolability of private property, organizing deep processing of agricultural products, and ensuring the accelerated development of regions.

In accordance with the tasks set out in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-5643 dated January 28, 2019 “On measures to improve the management system in the field of investment and foreign trade [2]”, significant work is being carried out in our country to improve the investment climate, increase export potential, and effectively regulate investment and foreign trade activities as a basis for the rapid development of business.

The essence of this decree is that due to the weak connection between the investment process and the final indicators of product promotion in foreign markets, the current system of public administration is based on separate regulation of investment and trade issues, which requires a revision of organizational and legal mechanisms in these areas.

In our opinion, in today’s world, at a time of globalization and technological advancement, the role of the investment environment in accelerating foreign trade is

becoming increasingly important and significant.

Literature review.

Having considered the factors influencing the formation of a favorable investment climate of a country/region, it should be noted that the state’s holistic representation in the world community in terms of investment attractiveness is of great importance. The strategy of moving the state’s investment reputation upwards is of great importance for attracting foreign direct investment [3].

“Investment potential” is interpreted as a set of investment resources, consisting of a part of the accumulated capital, which is manifested in the form of investment demand in the investment market, which has the potential to transform into real investment demand, ensuring the satisfaction of the material, financial and intellectual needs of capital reproduction [4].

The attractiveness of the investment environment, the economic development of each region depend on the potential of capital and labor resources, the level of their use. According to the generally accepted point of view, it is the economic potential of the region and its capabilities that are determined by the production of vital goods through the effective use of all the complex resources available there [5].

If the tendency of saving within a country is greater than investment, then exports in this country will exceed imports. If the opposite is true, then the volume of exports of such a country will be less than its imports. A country that consumes more than its capabilities seeks to make its exports exceed imports due to investments attracted from abroad. In this case, the attracted investments take the form of credit [6].

Companies in the country can determine the normative ratio between dividends and reinvestment in their dividend policy, protect the rights of minority shareholders, achieve an

increase in the market price of shares, and expand business activities, which will increase the investment attractiveness of companies, which will have a positive impact on the country's investment attractiveness [7].

Regardless of the field in which joint-stock companies operate in our republic, one of the important tasks is to allocate additional financial resources, including attracting foreign investments. One of the most modern ways to attract investments in joint-stock companies is to use the IPO mechanism [8].

Research methodology.

The article presents a graphical analysis of foreign trade indicators of foreign countries in terms of increasing foreign trade by improving the investment climate, schematizes some theoretical factors, and widely uses methods such as comparison, synthesis, and deduction.

Analysis and discussion of results.

In the current socio-economic conditions, the inflow of investments depends on the development of innovative sectors and the development of innovative entrepreneurship, the investment climate and the investment mechanism, if the investment climate is good, on the one hand, it allows for the growth of domestic investment, an increase in savings relative to consumption in the structure of planned expenditures. This is a guarantee of high economic growth rates.

In the course of studying scientific research on the regional economy, this study grouped the factors indicating the investment attractiveness of regions into a single system. In this, the main groups are summarized and classified as socio-economic potential, which is reflected in the complex indicators of the region, and scientific and practical views (Table 1).

Table 1. Classification of factors affecting the investment climate [9]

Nº	Group	Set of indicators
FACTORS AFFECTING THE LEVEL OF INVESTMENT CAPACITY OF REGIONS		
1	Natural and geographical potential	- raw material resources: mineral raw materials; land and water; fuel and energy; various ores and metals.
2	Production potential	- production capacities: gross regional product (GRP); condition of fixed assets; productivity of production factors; specialization of the region by sector and industry; volume of imports and exports.
3	Innovative potential	- the scientific and technical potential of the region: scientific and technical achievements; people with science and scientific degrees; the volume of scientific and technical projects; people engaged in science; scientific research and experimental design institutes/branches available in the region.
4	Infrastructure capacity	- infrastructure provision: the state of water and electricity available in the area; the presence of airports, roads and railways; the development of information and communication technologies.
5	Financial capacity	- the main criteria for financial capacity are: the volume of loans issued by commercial banks for the activities of business entities; the volume of funds placed by the population in bank deposits in national and foreign currencies; the volume of deposits of legal entities in banks (in national and foreign currencies).

The positive concentration of the above-mentioned diverse factors allows for the active inflow of foreign investments. This, of course, means additional jobs, additional income, and additional opportunities for economic growth. In addition, and most importantly, foreign

investors bring with them not only capital, but also advanced knowledge and experience that they have in their countries. This also creates opportunities for the country’s future economic growth.

Figure 1. Export performance of the top 10 Asian countries as of 2023 (in trillion US dollars) [10]

In the figure above, we can see that exports from Asia will total \$9.66 trillion in 2023. For the Asian countries as a whole, this dollar amount was \$7.719 trillion in 2019, a 25.1% increase over the 5-year trend. Also, international trade in products manufactured in Asia will account for 41.5% of the value of exports from all countries in the world.

Using statistics from the International Monetary Fund’s World Economic Outlook database, the total gross domestic product (GDP) for Asian countries in purchasing power

parity (PPP) terms is estimated to be about \$81.4 trillion in 2023. Therefore, Asia’s total exports of goods account for 11.9 percent of Asia’s economic output in terms of PPP-based GDP in 2023. Given Asia’s population of about 4.5 billion in 2023, the total \$9.66 trillion in exports from Asian countries amounts to about \$2,200 per person living in Asia. This dollar figure was higher than the average per capita of \$1,950 in 2022, a year earlier. This, in turn, indicates that the countries’ investment climate is stable.

Figure 2. Export performance of Central Asian countries as of 2023 (in billion US dollars) [11]

Based on the figure above, Armenia (up 57.7%), Kyrgyzstan (up 46.8%), Vietnam (up 22.3%), Mongolia (up 20.9%), Uzbekistan (up 18.5%), and then Cambodia (up 15.6%) recorded double-digit percentage growth in total exports. The countries whose exports declined sharply in 2023 were East Timor (down -65.3% compared to 2022), Tajikistan (down -44.5%), and Georgia (down -21.7%). The Republic of Uzbekistan, a landlocked country in Central Asia with a southern border with Afghanistan, is expected to export \$18.1 billion worth of goods worldwide in 2023. This projected dollar amount represents a 26.3% increase from \$14.3 billion in 2019 five years ago. Year-on-year, we can see that the total value of Uzbekistan’s exports increased by 18.5% compared to \$15.3 billion in 2022. Based on the average exchange rate for 2023, the Uzbek soum has depreciated by -32.8% against the US dollar since 2019 and weakened by -6.2% from 2022 to 2023. The weakening of the national currency in 2023 forced Uzbekistan’s exports to be paid for in a relatively stronger US dollar. Also, the latest data on countries available in 2022 shows that 80% of Uzbekistan’s exports were purchased by importers from Russia (22.1% of Uzbekistan’s

total), mainland China (14.9%), Turkey (12.4%), and Kazakhstan (10.6%), Kyrgyzstan (7.9%), Afghanistan (4.5%), Tajikistan (3.3%), Turkmenistan (1.13%), Poland (1.08%), Azerbaijan (1.08%), Iran (1.06%) and Pakistan (1.05%).

In terms of continent, about two-thirds (66.9%) of Uzbekistan’s exports went to Asian countries, while 32.1% went to European importers. Uzbekistan exported another 0.5% of its products to North America, with smaller percentages going to buyers in North America (0.5%), Africa (0.4%), Latin America (0.1%) excluding Mexico but including the Caribbean, and then only to Fiji and Australia in Oceania (0.001%). Considering Uzbekistan’s population of 36 million, its total exports of \$18.1 billion in 2023 would amount to about \$500 per capita per European citizen. This average dollar amount has increased from \$450 per capita a year earlier in 2022.

The following export product groups represent the highest dollar value of Uzbekistan’s global shipments through 2023. Each export category is also shown as a percentage of total exports from Uzbekistan (Table 2).

Table 2. Volume of exports of goods and products in the Republic of Uzbekistan as of 2023 [11]

Nº	Products and goods	Billion US dollars	Compared to 2022
1	Gems, precious metals	US\$11 billion	Up by 158.7%
2	Copper	\$1.1 billion	Down by -3.4%
3	Fertilizers	\$781.4 million	Up by 150%
4	Cotton	\$744.8 million	Down by -52.4%
5	Mineral fuels including oil	\$276.8 million	Reversing a -\$577.8 million deficit
6	Vegetables	\$232.6 million	Down by -38.8%
7	Inorganic chemicals	\$178.3 million	Reversing a -\$30.3 million deficit
8	Fruits, nuts	\$142.4 million	Down by -71.2%
9	Zinc	\$108.2 million	Down by -54.3%
10	Other base metals	\$48.8 million	Up by 84.4%

In the table above, we can see that precious stones and precious metals accounted for about \$11 billion (61% of total exports), copper \$1.1 billion (6%), fertilizers \$915.7 million (5.1%), cotton \$792.7 million (4.4%), mineral fuels, including oil \$719.1 million (4%), automobiles \$426.8 million (2.4%), machinery, including computers \$310.1 million (1.7%), plastics, plastic products \$281.5 million (1.6%), agricultural products, vegetables \$281.3 million (1.6%), fruits, nuts \$253.4 million (1.4%), and precious stones and precious metals grew by 156.2% from 2022 to 2023. However, in the balance of payments, net exports represent the amount by which a country's foreign spending on its own goods or services exceeds or lags behind its own country's spending on foreign goods or services. The products that caused Uzbekistan's largest trade deficit had a total trade deficit of -\$10.6 billion in 2023, a decrease of -18.6 percent from -\$13 billion in 2022. This, in turn, indicates that the country's foreign trade practices are improving year after year.

The above studies show that the stability of the investment climate affects the country's manufacturing sector, as well as the growth of industrial enterprises, and at the same time, the increase in the number of export-oriented goods and services. This determines the macroeconomic image of the country.

Conclusion and suggestions.

Summarizing the above analysis and considerations, it should be noted that in the context of intensifying modernization processes, it is appropriate for the state's medium and long-term investment strategy to focus on solving the following tasks:

1. Developing models for the efficient use of capital resources and the optimal use of

economic resources in increasing regional wealth, based on the law of finite depletion of factors;

2. To develop and implement comprehensive programs that will ensure the sustainable development of regions and their uniform development without significant differences;

3. To create a favorable business environment that will serve to organize joint projects based on high technologies and create high added value;

4. To maintain high and stable rates of economic growth at the same time, it is necessary to form a stable and competitive model of the country's economy, in which a significant part of the assets of the banking system are in the hands of private investors;

5. To increase investment attractiveness and ensure the rapid growth of investments in infrastructure, which is one of the main factors of sustainable economic growth, it is necessary to stimulate investment activity through the development of public-private partnerships and project financing instruments;

6. Optimize relations between investors and the state in order to completely eliminate bureaucratic obstacles and restrictions in the implementation of investment projects through digitalization and remote provision of public services.

Based on the above scientific suggestions and recommendations, their in-depth study, analysis and substantiated implementation in practice will yield results in the near future. In addition, it will have a positive impact on further increasing the investment attractiveness of the state by creating a favorable investment climate in the country.

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